

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

nextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Rare Diseases Community

Emidio Capriotti (University of Bologna)

European Life Sciences Infrastructure for Biological Information

www.elixir-europe.org

Major challenges of rare disease

RARE DISEASES

7% OF THE POPULATION ARE AFFECTED BY RARE DISEASES

THE EU CLASSES A DISEASE AS 'RARE' WHEN LESS THAN 1 IN 2000 SUFFER

OVER 6000 DISEASES
>70% GENETIC
~70% PEDIATRIC ONSET
OFTEN CHRONIC & LIFE-

DIAGNOSIS & TREATMENT
CHALLENGING & COSTLY

- 10 year global community vision (**IRDiRC**, 2017) *enable all people living with a Rare Disease (RD) to receive an accurate **diagnosis**, **care**, and available **therapy** within one year of coming to medical attention*
- Major **challenges**
 - Resources fragmented
 - Scarce, sensitive human data
 - How to find, access, interoperate, analyse?
- Requirement: infrastructure for **efficient**, cross-resource, cross-national analysis

Implementation Study 2022-2023

*to consolidate and demonstrate **efficiency gain** by European infrastructure for IRDiRC goals (earlier diagnosis, better care, more treatments)* Nodes: NL, ES, FR, LU, CH, IT, UK, BE, DE, SI, GR

COORDINATION

Coordination of the ELIXIR Rare Disease Community and cross-national interactions

Map required components in rare disease projects to ELIXIR services; work with the rare disease projects on quality and sustainability of services (e.g. EJP RD virtual platform)

FAIR EXPLOITATION

Demonstrate exploitation of FAIR data to reduce analytics complexity for data scientists

ANALYSIS SERVICES

Consolidate recently created ELIXIR Rare Disease Service Collections

DISSEMINATION & TRAINING

Disseminate and provide training on services and developments from the ELIXIR Rare Disease Community with the ELIXIR Training Platform

Coordination of ELIXIR RD Community (WP1)

Nodes: NL, ES, FR, LU, CH, IT, UK, BE, DE, SI, GR

Objective: to ensure continuity of aligning and **interconnecting international Rare Disease infrastructures** and projects with the general ELIXIR infrastructure and **services provided by ELIXIR nodes, communities and platforms.**

- **Map and align** with existing Rare Disease infrastructures, projects and initiatives
- **Exchange** experiences and results between projects
- Coordinate with **federated human data** on annotation, retrieval, and FAIRness of RD-relevant studies in federated EGA
- **Governance** of RD community, uptake/co-creation ELIXIR services
- Connect with **other communities** & health data sharing initiatives
- Collaborate with ELIXIR platforms and working groups on **topics not yet covered by RD community**, and new service collections
- **Expand** to nodes not yet participating

Demonstrate exploitation of FAIR data to reduce analytics complexity (WP2)

Nodes: NL, LU, CH, IT

- In the field of Oncology, algorithms continuously learn from **data across the globe** to improve chemotherapy recommendations

- **No data are moved!!!**

- **We also want this for rare diseases!**

Importance of ontologized data

Elements for sources to be VP compliant

Source (patient registry, Orphanet, WikiPathways, NextProt)

Ontological data and metadata

→ FAIR data point (metadata repository + API)

- The **rare disease community** (ELIXIR, EJP RD, RDs GO FAIR, patient organisations) is making **more resources FAIR**
- Example: resources within the EJP RD **FAIR & Federated Virtual Platform**
- Community **not yet aware** of the potential of **machine-actionable data and metadata**

A substrate for network-based discovery methods and Machine Learning

Objective: to demonstrate the exploitation of federated knowledge graphs resulting from machine-actionable FAIR data

Approach

- **Define** minimum requirements for **different types of data** to be usable for FAIR data analytics, i.e. the **ontologies** that form the **knowledge graph**
- **Investigate** the minimum information required for **aligning FAIR data** with existing **FAIR data analytics algorithms (tools/workflows)**
- **Evaluate** the benefits of FAIR data analytics based on **minimum requirements**
- **Coordinate** with the **ELIXIR interoperability platform** and **ML working group**

ELIXIR RD Data Analysis Service (WP3)

Nodes: ES, IT, NL, FR, DE, UK, BE, SI, LU

Task 3.1 “Assessing Molecular Pathogenicity for Rare Diseases”.

Leads: ELIXIR-IT, ELIXIR-FR

Task 3.2 “Systems Biology Service Bundles for Rare Diseases”.

Lead: ELIXIR-NL

Task 3.3 Evaluation and usage of GA4GH products for RD research.

Leads: ELIXIR-ES, ELIXIR-NL

Assessing Molecular Pathogenicity for Rare Diseases

- Generation of a **curated catalogue of the available resources and tools for the detection and interpretation of genetic variants at DNA and Protein levels.**
 - build on the available RD catalogue in bio.tools initiated by the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE (<https://rare-diseases.bio.tools/>)
 - consider other relevant services (publications, Galaxy workflows, WorkflowHub and TESS).
- Design and customise AMP4RD workflows based on **different user profiles.**

Systems Biology Service Bundles for Rare Diseases

The main objective of the task will be to **make the workflows developed in EJP RD FAIRly available:**

- development of ELIXIR concept map, including concepts about how to import and export data to/from a FAIR data point.
- tools will be linked to the corresponding entry in bio.tools, teaching materials will be added to TeSS and the EDAM ontology will be expanded as required to develop the workflows. These actions will be done in collaboration with the respective services.

Evaluation and usage of GA4GH products for RD research

Broad **adoption of GA4GH standards** should enable data and infrastructure interoperability, thus facilitating the **transition to federated infrastructures** such as those that will be needed in the **1+MG initiative**.

- Comparison of Phenopackets vs HL7/FHIR in the context of the RD-Connect GPAP and 1+MG RD Use Case
- Workflow interoperability demonstrator across cloud computing infrastructures such as EJP-RD/Solve-RD cloud, the ELIXIR Compute Platform and EOSC.

Disseminate and provide training on services and developments (WP4)

Nodes: IT, SI, ES, NL, FR, GR

Objective: to gather software development, data analysis and bioinformatics training needs within the RD community, and match and promote training that is already available to fulfil these needs

Approach:

- Survey training needs together with the training platform (update)
- Identify and promote across ELIXIR computing and data analysis training events relevant for the Rare Disease community
- Make selected materials, tools and services available in e-learning format using the ELIXIR-SI Moodle-based platform
- Promote the use of TeSS for disseminating events

Italian nodes involved in the Implementation Study

- Coordination and promotion of the activity of the Rare Disease community in Italy with direct involvement of 8 institutions

- Organization of a national infrastructure for genome annotation in the context of the RD and FHD communities.

Contribution of the Italian community

- Organization of the Service Collection 1 of the RD Community for the assessment of the molecular pathogenicity of the genetic variants (<https://amp4rd.github.io/>).
- Curation of the [RD bio.tools registry](#) and development of tools for variant annotation (SNPs&GO, INPS, PhD-SNP^g) and database curation (MINT, Signor, Disnor, Cancer GeneNet, Galactosemia Proteins DB).
- Organization of national and international meetings for the FAIRification of the data registry and the Rome BYOD to link RD registries.
- Identification and development of a “digital environment” for RD training.
- Participation to [Solve RD](#), [RD Connect](#), [Beacon](#) and [UDNI](#) networks.
- Participation to the EU Project Horizon 2020 [EJP-RD](#). Partner in 2 WPs (i) [Data Management & Quality Trainings](#) (ii) [Online Academic Education Course](#).

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ELIXIR-IT Rare Disease Workshop (Day 1)

Tuesday, 28th November 2023 - Sala lettura A (Biblioteca) CNR, P.le Aldo Moro 7	
14:30 - 15:00	Elixir IT: Rita Casadio UNIBO, Emidio Capriotti UNIBO, Claudio Carta ISS: The Italian Rare Disease Community
15:00 - 15:30	Elixir NL: European RD Communities. Marco Roos (ONLINE)
15:30 - 16:00	Elixir UK: Research Data Management. Munazah Andrabi (ONLINE)
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee break
16:30 - 17:00	Rare Disease Patient Representatives Annalisa Scopinaro, President of UNIAMO, Federazione Italiana Malattie Rare, Rome, Italy (ONLINE)
17:00 - 17:30	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS): Rare disease activities. Domenica Taruscio (ONLINE), Former Director National Centre for Rare Diseases
17:30-18:00	Ospedale Bambin Gesù: Orphanet Italia. Michele Nutini

ELIXIR-IT Rare Disease Workshop (Day 2)

Wednesday, 29th November 2023 - Sala lettura A (Biblioteca) CNR, P.le Aldo Moro 7	
09:30 - 11:00	<p>Presentations by young researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Giulia Babbi. UNIBO. Reactome pathways and Rare Diseases.• Damiano Parrone. UNIROMA1. A resource to explore drug repurposing opportunities for rare conformational diseases.• Cesare Rollo. UNITO. Deciphering Myelodysplastic Syndrome: A Deep Learning Approach for Prognosis Prediction and genomic Characterization.• Giulia Sassi. UNIPR. Illuminating Pharos TDarks: a coevoluzionario approach to rare diseases.• Bernardina Scafuri. UNISA. Identification of two possible pharmacochaperones for GALTp.Q188R enzyme by a computational strategy.
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 13:00	<p>Rare disease diagnosis: Use case presentations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Michele Pinelli, Università Federico II, Napoli Genomic annotation for the interpretation of DNA sequencing in rare diseases.• Tania Giangregorio, Ospedale Sant'Orsola, Bologna Workflows for the analysis of CNVs from microarray and NGS data.• Maria Cerminara, Istituto Gaslini, Genova Complex cases with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), developmental delay, hyperactivity and sleep disturbance explained by possible oligogenic mechanisms.• Alfredo Brusco, Università di Torino. Disentangling uncommon genetic causes of neurodevelopmental disorders. <p>Perspectives and closing</p>